

Replication of a Case Study Through the Application of Action Research to Promote Industry-Academia Collaboration

I. GUIDE TO THE QUESTIONNAIRE APPLIED TO STUDENTS

Part1 - Demographic profile of the respondent

RQ1: Are you: professional, student or both

RQ2: What is your level of education?

RQ3: What is your current position?

RQ4: How many years of experience do you have in your current position? If you are an undergraduate student there is How long have you been in graduation? If you are a postgraduate student, how long have you been working in the market?

RQ5: How many years of IT experience (in years)?

RQ6: How old are you?

RQ7: What is your gender?

Part 2 - Team size and project duration

RQ8: The size of the team of students conducted in the Action Research influenced positively or negatively in the use of Action Research?

RQ9: Did the duration of the project positively or negatively influence the application of Action Research?

Part 3: Challenges and Benefits of Using Action Research

RQ10: Were there any challenges in the Planning phase?

RQ11: Were there any challenges in the Intervention/Action phase?

RQ12: Were there any challenges in the Assessment phase?

RQ13: Were there any challenges in the Reflection phase?

RQ14: Which stage of the Action Research did you/your team have the most difficulty executing?

(Planning, Intervention/Action, Assessment or Reflection)

Part 4: Challenges and Benefits for Industry/Academia with the application of Action Research

RQ15: In your opinion, the choice of this method was representative for strengthening ties between the academia and industry?

RQ16: Do you believe that the industry is open to applying this research method?

RQ17: What are the main benefits of applying Action Research to academia?

RQ18: What are the main challenges of applying Action Research to academia?

RQ19: What are the main **benefits** of applying Action Research to Industry/Government?

RQ20: What are the main **challenges** of applying Action Research to Industry/Government?

Part 5: Satisfaction

RQ21: Did you know the Action Research method before the course?

RQ22: How satisfied are you in the discipline with the use of Action Research?

RQ23: How do you evaluate the assessment model used in the course (360 assessment)?

RQ24: Would you enroll in other subjects with the same teacher?

Part 6: Learning Insights

RQ25: Does having an assistant teacher (monitor) help with learning?

RQ26: After using the Action Research method in the discipline, do you consider it relevant to your learning?